

Supplementary Information

Future cost of climate change for humanitarian crises

Other supplementary information stored as a replication package at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15336209> include:

1. The dataset file containing all raw data, exact metadata and subsequent transformation, correction, deletion or imputation.
2. All Python scripts to run the model (baseline + simulation).
3. Model results used to produce figures and claims in the paper.
4. All country graph reports from each model run (baseline + simulations).
5. The R script used for conflict exposure imputation.
6. The Python-based plotters of the figures in the paper.

Table of Contents

1. TRAINING DATASET	2
VARIABLES AND DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS.....	2
TRANSFORMATIONS.....	5
MOST INFLUENTIAL VARIABLES.....	6
ANALYSED COUNTRIES.....	7
EXPOSURE SHARES IN THE DATASET	7
2. GPR MODEL CODE SPECIFICATION	10
GAUSSIAN PROCESS FORMALLY	10
BUILD GAUSSIAN PROCESS REGRESSION PIPELINE	11
SIMULATION DEFINITION	12
3. MODEL DIAGNOSTICS	12
GOODNESS OF FIT.....	12
CROSS-VALIDATION	13
RESIDUAL VISUAL INSPECTION	14
ROBUSTNESS CHECKS	14
4. INITIAL VARIABLE IMPORTANCE ANALYSIS	22
5. PRELIMINARY ASSESSMENTS OF THE DATASET	24
CORRELATION.....	24
MULTICOLLINEARITY.....	25
AUTOCORRELATION.....	25
HETEROSKEDASTICITY.....	26
STATIONARITY	27
6. BASELINE COUNTRY GRAPHS	28
7. MARGINAL EFFECT PLOTS OF THE PREDICTORS	32
8. EXTENDED DATA	33
9. LIST OF FIGURES AND TABLES	37

1. Training dataset

Here we summarize the set used to train the model. All raw data, exact metadata, and subsequent transformations are available in full detail at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15336209>.

Variables and descriptive statistics

Table 1 Descriptions of variables

VARIABLE	UNIT	DESCRIPTION
MAIN RESPONSE VARIABLE IN PHASE 1		
<i>ΣEX</i>	million persons	<p>Nominal people at risk. That is, the sum of people analytically exposed per country to different hazards from INFORM Risk and INFORM Climate Change. The summed subcategories are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. EX_DENMAL = average between people exposed to dengue and malaria 2. EX_CFL = exposed to coastal floods 3. EX_EQ_MMI6 = exposed to earthquakes with Modified Mercalli Intensity higher than 6 4. EX_FL = exposed to river floods 5. EX_TC_SS1 = exposed to tropical cyclone winds with Saffir-Simpson category higher than 1 6. EX_TS = exposed to tsunamis 7. EX_DR = exposed to drought based on 12-month standardized precipitation and evapotranspiration indices (SPI/SPEI), 8. EX_CON = exposed to conflict (indicator built by authors) <p>Each subcategory is summed up regardless of possible overlap. See INFORM metadata in the dataset file or in links for further info: (https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/inform-index/INFORM-Climate-Change and https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/inform-index/INFORM-Risk)</p>
INITIAL PREDICTORS IN PHASE 1 (GLOBAL)		
<i>SST_global</i>	°C	Global average temperature of seawater near the surface. (https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.5292a2b0)
<i>GSATA_global</i>	K	Change in global average near-surface air temperatures over land, oceans and sea ice above pre-industrial levels (1850-1900). (https://data.ece.iiasa.ac.at/ar6)
<i>SFCWIND_global</i>	m s ⁻¹	Global average near-surface wind speed. The magnitude of the two-dimensional horizontal air velocity near the surface. (https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.5292a2b0)
<i>PR_global</i>	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Global average of the sum of liquid and frozen water, comprising rain and snow, that falls to the Earth's surface. It is the sum of large-scale

VARIABLE	UNIT	DESCRIPTION
		precipitation and convective precipitation. This parameter does not include fog, dew or the precipitation that evaporates in the atmosphere before it lands at the surface of the Earth. This variable represents the amount of water per unit area and time. https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.5292a2b0
INITIAL PREDICTORS IN PHASE 1 (COUNTRY-LEVEL)		
<i>POP</i>	million persons	Population of a given country. (https://data.ece.iiasa.ac.at/ssp)
<i>GDP</i>	billion USD ₂₀₂₄	Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) with US dollar prices in 2024. (https://data.ece.iiasa.ac.at/ssp and https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/datasets/WEO)
<i>HDI</i>	-	The Human Development Index is a summary measure of average achievement in key dimensions of human development: a long and healthy life, being knowledgeable and having a decent standard of living. The HDI is the geometric mean of normalized indices for each of the three dimensions. (https://hdr.undp.org/data-center/human-development-index#/indicies/HDI and https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-02941-6)
<i>cdd</i>	days	Maximum number of consecutive dry days. The maximum length of a dry spell, computed sequentially for the entire time series, then taking the maximum value during each month in the data period (a dry day is defined as any day in which the daily accumulated precipitation < 1 mm). (https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/)
<i>cdw</i>	days	Max Number of Consecutive Wet Days. This series measures the maximum length of a wet spell, computed sequentially for the entire time series, then taking the maximum value during each month in the data period (a wet day is defined as any day in which the daily accumulated precipitation ≥ 1 mm). (https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/)
<i>hd40</i>	days	The number of days with daily maximum temperature ≥ 40°C that occurred during the aggregation period. (https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/)
<i>pr</i>	mm	Aggregated accumulated precipitation. (https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/)
<i>r20mm</i>	days	The number of heavy precipitation days during the aggregation period. A heavy precipitation day for r20mm is defined as any day in which the daily accumulated precipitation is ≥ 20 mm. (https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/)
<i>rx5day</i>	mm	The average highest precipitation amounts over a consecutive 5-day period during each month in the data period. (https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/)
<i>tas</i>	°C	Average mean temperature over the aggregation period. (https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/)

VARIABLE	UNIT	DESCRIPTION
<i>net migration</i>	thousand persons	The net total of migrants during the period, that is, the number of immigrants minus the number of emigrants, including citizens and noncitizens. (https://databank.worldbank.org and www.wittgensteincentre.org/dataexplorer)
FINAL RESPONSE VARIABLES IN PHASES 2 AND 3		
<i>PIN</i>	million persons	The real people in need of humanitarian assistance per country according to the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UN OCHA). (https://humanitarianaction.info)
<i>funding requirement</i>	million USD _{nominal}	The funding required to provide humanitarian assistance to the people in need per country according to UN OCHA's analysis. (https://humanitarianaction.info)

Table 2 Descriptive statistics of the dataset

	count	mean	std (σ)	min	25%	50%	75%	max
ΣEX	312	40	57	2	14	23	38	513
<i>EX_DENMAL</i>	312	29	48	0	9	16	28	415
<i>EX_CFL</i>	312	0.03	0.18	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	2.45
<i>EX_EQ_MMI6</i>	312	0.03	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.25
<i>EX_FL</i>	312	0.27	0.43	0.00	0.03	0.12	0.27	3.81
<i>EX_TC_SS1</i>	312	0.06	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.98
<i>EX_TS</i>	312	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>EX_DR</i>	312	3.6	6.4	0.0	0.9	1.7	4.0	74.5
<i>EX_CON</i>	312	6.6	7.4	0.4	1.9	3.9	8.7	46.6
SST_global	2626	15	0	14	14	15	15	16
SFCWIND_global	2626	6.26	0.01	6.24	6.25	6.26	6.26	6.29
PR_global	2626	2.51	0.04	2.43	2.47	2.51	2.55	2.59
GSATA_global	2626	1.86	0.59	0.77	1.37	1.95	2.38	2.71
POP	2626	63	96	3	15	35	60	697
GDP	2626	880	2181	3	92	287	824	23983
HDI	2626	0.64	0.15	0.26	0.54	0.66	0.76	0.94
cdd	2626	101	75	8	43	72	169	252
cdw	2626	54	48	4	10	39	84	198
hd40	2626	24	37	0	0	5	36	156
pr	2626	1126	839	96	334	1003	1810	3538
r20mm	2626	6.9	8.6	0.2	1.1	3.2	9.0	35.4
rx5day	2626	75	38	18	45	74	96	201
tas	2626	25.4	4.5	8.9	24.5	26.4	28.3	31.6
net migration	2626	-24	153	-5699	-34	-17	-4	1146
PIN	168	9.3	8.2	0.6	3.3	5.8	13.6	37.1

	count	mean	std (σ)	min	25%	50%	75%	max
funding requirement	168	1625	2128	26	385	778	2283	11668

Transformations

For missing data, we have primarily used linear interpolation in simple cases, such as in missing interim years in GDP and population. Bias corrections between different time series have been performed based on a common year for between INFORM Climate Change and INFORM Risk, and HDI for the historic values with a Delta method assuming the change remains relatively constant throughout the years.

The most complex and novel transformation was done for conflict exposure (EX_CON). Here, conflict exposure was originally only expressed in probabilities in INFORM Climate Change and as intensities of conflict in INFORM Risk via the HIIK index or as conflict fatality. We based the exposure on INFORM's HA.HUM.CON.UCDP, CON.HIIK and CON.PROJECTED indicators (pp. 26-27 <https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/inform-index/INFORM-Climate-Change/Methodology>) as well as new ACLED (Armed Conflict Location and Event Data) data.

To build EX_CON, we followed the next steps:

1. The best estimate of exposed population to conflict is from ACLED Conflict Exposure Calculator for Political Violence and Organized Violence categories, see <https://acleddata.com/conflict-exposure/>.
2. Missing years 2015-2019 are most likely MCAR (missing completely at random) and thus, we used a log-linear regression with HIIK and CON_UCDP as predictors and COUNTRY and YEAR as fixed effect factors to impute them by training on the 2020-2024 data. The model ran 1 000 Monte Carlo simulations to account for uncertainty of the data, and the mean was used as the final imputation. The 2.5th and 97.5th percentile bounds, and the inferential statistics are displayed in the Excel file for sensitivity analysis. The model was run in R with the lm and mvnorm functions with the assistance of ChatGPT o3-mini-high. The R script ('conflict exposure imputation.R') is included in the Zenodo dump.
3. Finally, EX_CON is projected to 2050 and 2080 simply based on the 2022 ratio with CON.PROJECTED. The assumption is that the relationship stays static but otherwise follows the RCP4.5-SSP2 path and returns to this equilibrium regardless of other exogenous factors.

All transformations are explicitly recorded and displayed in the dataset file for each sheet corresponding to raw data at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15336209>.

Most influential variables

Although study was not intended to be inferential, the Gaussian Process Regression led to some insight on what it considers to be the climate risk drivers of humanitarian crises. It does so with the learned length scales of the covariance function (or kernel). In Table 3, the length scales that the GPR learned per each predictor variable in determining nominal people at risk are displayed. Marginal effect plots are at Figure 7.

Check also robustness tests in Table 8 because the length scales change depending on the model specification.

Table 3 Nominal people at risk indicators per length scale

Variable in model phase 1 (shorthand in dataset)	Importance (length scale ℓ_d , 0.01–100.0) \uparrow
Country-level: Surface air temperature (<i>tas</i>)	most influential 1.2
Country-level: Precipitation (<i>pr</i>)	2.0
Country-level: Population (<i>POP</i>)	4.7
Global: Change in surface air temperature relative to the industrial period (<i>GSATA_global</i>)	6.4
Country-level: Average highest precipitation over a consecutive 5-day period during each month (<i>rx5day</i>)	10.8
Country-level: Human Development Index (<i>HDI</i>)	11.6
Global: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sea surface temperature (<i>SST_global</i>) ○ Surface wind speed (<i>SFCWIND_global</i>) ○ Precipitation (<i>PR_global</i>) Country-level: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Gross Domestic Production (<i>GDP</i>) ○ Maximum of consecutive dry days (<i>cdd</i>) ○ Maximum of consecutive wet days (<i>cdw</i>) ○ Days over 40°C (<i>hd40</i>) ○ Heavy precipitation days (<i>r20mm</i>) ○ Net migration (<i>net migration</i>) 	practically irrelevant 100.0

Table Notes: These come from Eq. 1 in phase 1 of the model. We can interpret a shorter length scale to be a more impactful driver of nominal people at risk and vice versa. The Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) uses hyperparameter length scales ℓ_d to capture underlying patterns and complexity of the data as well as adapt to different scales in different dimensions. In the model, the GPR is allowed to optimize them within bounds of 0.01–100 to maximise the log-marginal likelihood, an indicator of model fit. A shorter length scale means that the values can change more rapidly, leading to a more agile function. Conversely, a longer length scale results in a smoother function where the function values change more slowly.

These are only applicable for the current model specification. Check against robustness tests in Supplementary Table 8 because the length scales change depending on the hyperparameters. Also check against the marginal effect plots in Supplementary Figure 7 because, for example, HDI increases people at risk and is likely a proxy or a factor for population in the GPR core model.

Analysed countries

Table 4 The 26 analysed countries with their 2022 ND-GAIN score

ISO3	Name in UN system	ND-GAIN	ISO3	Name in UN system	ND-GAIN
AFG	Afghanistan	33.2	MOZ	Mozambique	39.2
BDI	Burundi	35.9	NER	Niger	35.5
BFA	Burkina Faso	37.9	NGA	Nigeria	39.4
CAF	Central African Republic	27.9	PSE	occupied Palestinian territory	-
CMR	Cameroon	38.7	SDN	Sudan	32.7
COD	Democratic Republic of the Congo	32.5	SLV	El Salvador	46.1
COL	Colombia	48.7	SOM	Somalia	35.3
ETH	Ethiopia	38.7	SSD	South Sudan	-
GTM	Guatemala	43.7	SYR	Syrian Arab Republic	38.5
HND	Honduras	40.8	TCD	Chad	27.2
HTI	Haiti	35.3	UKR	Ukraine	52.3
MLI	Mali	34.2	VEN	Venezuela, Bolivarian Republic of	41.0
MMR	Myanmar	37.1	YEM	Yemen	36.2

Table Notes: These countries (including occupied Palestinian territory) had a [UN Humanitarian Response Plan \(HRP\) in 2023](#). The [ND-GAIN Index](#) score is a comparative figure for their vulnerability to climate change. For scale understanding, Norway has a score of 76.6 at rank 1, and Chad has the lowest score of 27.2 at rank 185.

Exposure shares in the dataset

We disaggregate original hazards from INFORM Risk and INFORM Climate Change to examine exposure drivers. The shares of exposure drivers here should be taken as an illustrative background only because it does not remove exposure overlap between the hazard categories and, for example, both the climate-conflict assumption and its exposure simulation are simplistic for the sake of actionability and to calculate the people in need from nominal people at risk. On pure hazard-share, more sophisticated studies of multiple hazard accounting should be favoured (e.g., [Stalhandske et al., 2025](#)).

The INFORM data suggests that epidemic exposure (primarily dengue and malaria here) is by far the most dominant driver in the 26 countries—accounting for 35-37% of all exposure at any time (Figure 1a). On the other hand, epidemic exposure can rationally be much more encompassing (e.g., COVID-19) than localised flood or tropical cyclone hazards. For example, [Mora et al. \(2022\)](#) found that pathways of pathogenic diseases aggravated by climate could be too numerous to be adaptable. However, the latitude around 33°N

(Afghanistan, occupied Palestinian territory, and Syrian Arab Republic) have a pronounced shift to a more dominant drought-based driver in 2050 and 2080.

After epidemics, conflict (10%) and drought (4%) are the most powering drivers in the current period of 2015–2024. In 2050 and 2080, drought (7% and 10%, respectively) would replace conflict (6% and 4%, respectively) as the 2nd most critical driver. The causal connection between conflict and climate change has important literature behind it (e.g., [Hsiang & Burke, 2014](#), [Damette & Gouette, 2023](#)) and is not fully resolved—especially on the drought before the Syrian Civil War ([Selby et al., 2017](#)).

River floods are the only additional one that significantly appear in the global average (3.3-3.9% at any time) while others have more localised exposure, such as tropical cyclones in Haiti and coastal flood in Guatemala.

Figure 1 Distribution of exposure drivers

Figure Notes: **Above:** The percentage distribution of each exposure driver in nominal people at risk (ΣEX) for each country in 2015-2024, 2050 and 2080. These are the periods where INFORM Risk and INFORM Climate Change had data or a projection. Their data has been rescaled, transformed and imputed. Global average is shown as last. We emphasise that this is a virtual metric because there is without a doubt overlap between the categories (for example, one person can be at the same time exposed to flood, drought, and conflict). **Below:** Same data and colouring, but dengue and malaria have been removed.

2. GPR model code specification

Gaussian Process formally

See [Rasmussen & Williams \(2006\)](#) and [Lyu et al. \(2024\)](#). The target values of the model come from a function drawn via a Gaussian Process Regression (GPR, also called GP prior), defined by a mean function and a kernel (covariance) function. These define the GP prior:

$$f(x) \sim GP(m(x), k(x, x'), \sigma_n^2 \delta_{x, x'}),$$

Where $m(x)$ is the mean function and the expected value of $f(x)$ before seeing any data. $k(x, x')$ is the covariance function defining how similar points x and x' are. The last two terms are the WhiteKernel kernel.

$m(x)$ is a choice. Here, we have set it up as $m(x) = 0$ everywhere, the most common choice. It basically means “before seeing any data, we don’t favour any systematic offset.” Once the model conditions on the data, the GP posterior mean will shift. Other options would be e.g., to have a constant mean $m(x) = c$ or a domain specific prior, such as a known climate trend from physics models.

The model of the paper fits the posterior mean entirely based on the kernel structure—an anisotropic RBF (radial basis function) and WhiteKernel—and the training data. Thus, the “shape” of the baseline is learned purely from the kernelized relationships in the predictors and observed data.

An anisotropic RBF kernel (or squared exponential or Gaussian kernel) essentially means that we believe the target variable changes smoothly with respect to each predictor, but that smoothness can be different for each predictor dimension. Formally, RBF between two points x and x' is:

$$k(x, x') = \sigma^2 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{d=1}^D \frac{(x_d - x'_d)^2}{\ell_d^2}\right)$$

Where σ^2 is the signal variance that controls the vertical scale of the kernel, ℓ_d is the length scale for dimension D and controls smoothness, and D is the number of input dimensions (predictors). In an isotropic version, all predictors affect the output over roughly the same “distance” scale and ℓ_d is the same. In anisotropic, each predictor can learn its own ℓ_d . This allows the model to identify which features are more relevant.

For example, in this study, there was a short ℓ_d for tas and pr meaning small changes in temperature or precipitation can lead to noticeable changes in people at risk. Likewise, long ℓ_d for variables like SST_global means the GP treats them as nearly constant over the relevant scale. (Table 3.) Essentially, they don't move the needle much in explaining ΣEX .

Thus, the kernel assumption is that (1) the relationship between climatic-socioeconomic predictors and humanitarian needs is smooth (no sharp discontinuities) in each predictor dimension. That smoothness varies per predictor, and the GP will discover these scales from the data rather than imposing them a priori.

A WhiteKernel noise is added on top of RBF (defined as ϵ in the paper's regression function). It adds noise to the observations, such as measurement error in regression. Without it, the GPR would not assume noise which is unrealistic. Likewise, it prevents overfitting:

$$\sigma_n^2 \delta_{x,x'}$$

Where σ_n^2 is the noise variance learned during the training and $\delta_{x,x'}$ is the Kronecker delta (1 if $x = x'$, otherwise 0).

Below is the specification used in main part of the code for the Gaussian Process Regression as well as for the simulation definition (see more at scikit-learn's [page on GPR](#)). The Python 3.12 scripts are openly stored on <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15336209> along with their random seed (42).

Build Gaussian Process Regression pipeline

```
def build_pipeline(rbf_bounds=(1e-2,1e2), noise_init=None, noise_bounds=(1e-2,1e2),
n_restarts=5):

    rbf = RBF(length_scale=np.ones(len(PREDICTORS)), length_scale_bounds=rbf_bounds)
    white = (WhiteKernel(noise_level=noise_init, noise_level_bounds=noise_bounds)
            if noise_init is not None else WhiteKernel(noise_level_bounds=noise_bounds))
    gpr = GaussianProcessRegressor(
        kernel=rbf + white,
        normalize_y=True,
        n_restarts_optimizer=n_restarts,
        random_state=42
    )
    return Pipeline([('scaler', RobustScaler()), ('gpr', gpr)])
```

Simulation definition

```
pin_shocks = [  
  # All the numbers in the below specification come from the simulation table in the  
  paper's Methods section.  
  # Now, it is in the 'worst' mode. Any other simulation can be replicated by adjusting the  
  specification.  
  ShockEvent(  
    name="TEMPORARY SHOCKS 1",  
    annual_prob=1/8,  
    dist_fn=lambda n: np.random.lognormal(np.log(1.3), 0.25, size=n),  
    start_year=2025,  
    half_life_dist_fn=lambda: np.random.lognormal(np.log(2), 0.25),  
  ),  
  ShockEvent(  
    name="TEMPORARY SHOCKS 2",  
    annual_prob=1/20,  
    dist_fn=lambda n: np.random.lognormal(np.log(2.1), 0.25, size=n),  
    start_year=2025,  
    half_life_dist_fn=lambda: np.random.lognormal(np.log(6), 0.25),  
  ),  
]  
drift_shock = DriftShockEvent(  
  name="STRUCTURAL BREAK",  
  start_year=2025,  
  coverage_dist_fn = lambda: np.random.beta(a=15, b=5), # NB! A beta distribution  
  corresponding approx to 75% with  $\pm 9.4\%$  SD  
  drift_rate_dist_fn = lambda: np.random.normal(0.02, 0.0005),  
)
```

3. Model diagnostics

Goodness of fit

Table 5 Global diagnostics of the final Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) model

RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error)	3.15
MAE (Mean Absolute Error)	2.14
R^2 (Coefficient of Determination)	0.997
Log Marginal Likelihood	207.62
Noise Variance σ^2	0.01
Coverage $\pm 1\sigma$	93.9
Coverage $\pm 2\sigma$	100

Shapiro–Wilk W (normality)	0.93
Shapiro–Wilk p (normality)	6.66E-11

Table 6 Country-level diagnostics

ISO3	RMSE ↓	R ²	MAE	Bias	ISO3	RMSE (cont. ↓)	R ²	MAE	Bias
NGA	7.24	0.9939	6.03	-0.54	MOZ	2.1	0.9403	1.66	-0.85
MMR	6.05	0.624	4.77	-1.18	YEM	2.1	0.8453	1.42	0.27
COD	4.84	0.9774	4.08	-0.3	ETH	2.01	0.9876	1.79	0.73
SDN	4.73	0.8461	3.97	-0.08	CAF	1.99	-2.4111	1.27	1.27
SOM	4.47	-1.6695	2.9	1	SLV	1.93	-1.1356	1.58	1.17
CMR	3.11	0.7868	2.38	-0.2	SSD	1.73	0.6858	1.21	-0.92
UKR	3.05	0.7962	2.15	0.15	SYR	1.71	0.821	1.33	-0.3
VEN	2.96	0.7383	2.27	-0.87	PSE	1.68	-3.3589	1.02	0.38
GTM	2.92	0.9774	2.1	-1.35	BFA	1.62	0.982	1.2	-0.41
NER	2.91	0.7157	2.44	0.84	TCD	1.35	0.9601	1.25	0.95
AFG	2.86	0.8146	2.27	-0.14	MLI	1.22	0.988	1.04	0.52
COL	2.68	0.8378	2.38	0.59	BDI	1.01	0.6828	0.8	0.03
HTI	2.5	-0.594	1.54	-1.48	HND	1.01	0.8762	0.86	0.34

Table Notes: Bias is the difference between average predicted values and average observed values.

Cross-validation

Table 7 Cross-Validation (CV) and nested CV diagnostics

Fold	1	2	3	4	5
CV					
RMSE	9.85	3.55	12.30	4.63	89.89
MAE	4.48	2.58	5.54	2.91	31.76
R ²	0.95	0.99	0.94	0.99	0.00
Test Years	2017,2018	2019,2020	2021,2022	2023,2024	2050,2080
NESTED CV					
RMSE	42.97	46.88	52.32	54.68	93.29
MAE	23.08	24.62	26.73	28.16	40.58
R ²	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01	-0.02	-0.08
Best_length_scale_bounds	0.1, 100.0	0.01, 100.0	0.1, 100.0	0.01, 100.0	0.1, 100.0
Best_noise_level_bounds	0.01, 10.0	0.01, 100.0	0.01, 10.0	0.01, 100.0	0.01, 100.0
Test Years	2017,2018	2019,2020	2021,2022	2023,2024	2050,2080

Residual visual inspection

Figure 2 Global residuals of the GPR model

Figure Notes: There are some left-over heavy tails, heteroskedasticity, and persistent time memory after the GPR model's fitting. These are discussed more in the paper.

Robustness checks

During the GPR run of the paper itself, the Python script gives multiple convergence warnings where the optimal value found for either length scale ℓ_d or noise σ^2 is close to the specified lower (0.01) or upper bound (100). Hence, we have here prepared robustness tests on different hyperparameters and other choices (Table 8).

Differences in the grand total of $\sum EX$ compared to the paper seem to appear from the blow up in large population countries, such as Democratic Republic of the Congo and Nigeria. Thus, their “contribution” to the grand total diminishes significantly. The GPR would like to have as low of a noise variance σ^2 as possible (to a lower bound of 0.000619) to optimise the log marginal likelihood, but this is clearly not realistic, and some countries visually behave

inconsistently. Thus, diagnostic calculation can result in overfitting if not validated by a domain expert.

Adding optimizer restarts, changing the scaler, or changing absolute GDP PPP to GDP PPP per capita in the dataset did not result in almost any changes except that it replaced HDI as the regressor (Table 8d-f). Hence, the core GPR model is mostly sensitive to the hyperparameters, especially to the lower bound of the noise σ^2 and upper bound of length scale ℓ_a . Because no length scale went below 0.96, but the upper bound of 100 000 was reached by multiple.

Out of the paper's learned length scales, POP and pr are the only variables that stay influential in all variations of the hyperparameters. GSAT Δ _global and rx5day are influential in panels b-c while tas only in panel b. HDI is not influential in any of panels a-c, but GDP is. Other extreme event indicators, such as cdd, cdw, hd40, and r20mm become influential in panels b-c.

The grand total of $\sum EX$ is particularly robust till 2050 in all checks with a maximum difference of -12 to the paper. In 2075, the difference can be as high as -476 (Table 8b) and -589 in 2100 (Table 8c). In these learned length scales, population becomes the most dominant explainer.

Table 8 Robustness tests by modifying hyperparameters (a-e) and GDP (f)

a

Length scale ℓ_d bounds and noise σ^2 bounds: 0.1 and 10	
Optimizer restarts: 5	
RobustScaler	
RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error)	5.86
MAE (Mean Absolute Error)	3.51
R ² (Coefficient of Determination)	0.9895
Log Marginal Likelihood	-73.14
Noise Variance σ^2	0.1
Coverage $\pm 1\sigma$	99
Coverage $\pm 2\sigma$	100
Shapiro–Wilk W (normality)	0.86
Shapiro–Wilk p (normality)	2.91E-16
<i>Visual Inspection of country plots: NGA blows up. It has super unrealistic dips outside of the training (-2024, 2050, 2080). COD does a suspicious dip right after the last training point 2080.</i>	
2025 Grand Total of $\sum EX$ (difference from paper)	1051 (-49)
2050 “	1479 (-12)
2075 “	1420 (-244)
2100 “	1181 (-380)
Feature (most influential six in the paper in green)	LengthScale ℓ_d
POP	2.05
pr	4.82
SST_global	10
SFCWIND_global	10
PR_global	10
GSATA_global	10
GDP	10
HDI	10
cdd	10
cdw	10
hd40	10
r20mm	10
rx5day	10
tas	10
Net migration	10

b

Length scale ℓ_d bounds and noise σ^2 bounds: 0.001 and 1 000

Optimizer restarts: 5

RobustScaler

RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error)	1.31
MAE (Mean Absolute Error)	0.94
R ² (Coefficient of Determination)	0.9995
Log Marginal Likelihood	324.95
Noise Variance σ^2	0.001
Coverage $\pm 1\sigma$	89.4
Coverage $\pm 2\sigma$	98.7
Shapiro–Wilk W (normality)	0.98
Shapiro–Wilk p (normality)	1.99E-06

Visual Inspection of country plots: COD and NGA blow up. They have super unrealistic dips outside of the training (-2024, 2050, 2080).

2025 Grand Total of $\sum EX$ (difference from paper)	1097 (-3)
2050 “	1486 (-5)
2075 “	1188 (-476)
2100 “	1048 (-513)

Feature (most influential six in the paper in green)	LengthScale ℓ_d
POP	1.06
pi	1.87
rx5day	2.42
GDP	4.92
GSATA_global	5.58
tas	5.72
cdd	13.83
hd40	14.59
r20mm	14.78
Net migration	71.90
SST_global	1000.00
SFCWIND_global	1000.00
PR_global	1000.00
HDI	1000.00
cdw	1000.00

c

Length scale ℓ_d bounds and noise σ^2 bounds: 0.0001 and 10 000

Optimizer restarts: 5

RobustScaler

RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error)	1.08
MAE (Mean Absolute Error)	0.75
R ² (Coefficient of Determination)	0.9996
Log Marginal Likelihood	329.87
Noise Variance σ^2	0.000619
Coverage $\pm 1\sigma$	89.7
Coverage $\pm 2\sigma$	98.7
Shapiro–Wilk W (normality)	0.94
Shapiro–Wilk p (normality)	1.6E-09

Visual Inspection of country plots: COD, ETH, and NGA blow up. They have super unrealistic dips outside of the training (-2024, 2050, 2080).

2025 Grand Total of $\sum EX$ (difference from paper)	1085 (-15)
2050 “	1486 (-5)
2075 “	1209 (-455)
2100 “	972 (-589)

Feature (most influential six in the paper in green)	LengthScale ℓ_d
POP	0.97
pi	1.65
cdw	2.20
rx5day	3.35
GDP	4.07
GSATA_global	5.52
cdd	6.64
hd40	8.06
Net migration	34.85
r20mm	9157.77
SST_global	10000.00
SFCWIND_global	10000.00
PR_global	10000.00
HDI	10000.00
tas	10000.00

d

Length scale ℓ_d bounds and noise σ^2 bounds: 0.01 and 100

Optimizer restarts: 10

RobustScaler

RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error)	3.15
MAE (Mean Absolute Error)	2.14
R ² (Coefficient of Determination)	0.997
Log Marginal Likelihood	207.62
Noise Variance σ^2	0.01
Coverage $\pm 1\sigma$	93.9
Coverage $\pm 2\sigma$	100
Shapiro-Wilk W (normality)	0.93
Shapiro-Wilk p (normality)	6.66E-11

Visual Inspection of country plots: All stable.

2025 Grand Total of $\sum EX$ (difference from paper)	1100 (0)
2050 “	1491 (0)
2075 “	1664 (0)
2100 “	1561 (0)

Feature (most influential six in the paper in green)	LengthScale ℓ_d
tas	1.22
pr	1.96
POP	4.74
GSATA_global	6.40
rx5day	10.79
HDI	11.60
SST_global	100.00
SFCWIND_global	100.00
PR_global	100.00
GDP	100.00
cdd	100.00
cdw	100.00
hd40	100.00
r20mm	100.00
Net migration	100.00

e

Length scale ℓ_d bounds and noise σ^2 bounds: 0.01 and 100

Optimizer restarts: 5

StandardScaler

RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error)	3.20
MAE (Mean Absolute Error)	2.17
R ² (Coefficient of Determination)	0.9969
Log Marginal Likelihood	213.71
Noise Variance σ^2	0.01
Coverage $\pm 1\sigma$	92.90
Coverage $\pm 2\sigma$	100
Shapiro–Wilk W (normality)	0.93
Shapiro–Wilk p (normality)	4.86E-11

Visual Inspection of country plots: All stable.

2025 Grand Total of $\sum EX$ (difference from paper)	1103 (+3)
2050 “	1491 (0)
2075 “	1663 (-1)
2100 “	1589 (+28)

Feature (most influential six in the paper in green)	LengthScale ℓ_d
tas	0.96
GSATA_global	2.47
POP	2.59
pr	3.38
rx5day	13.57
HDI	20.41
hd40	49.68
SST_global	100.00
SFCWIND_global	100.00
PR_global	100.00
GDP	100.00
cdd	100.00
cdw	100.00
r20mm	100.00
Net migration	100.00

f

Absolute GDP PPP replaced with GDP PPP per capita

RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error)	3.13
MAE (Mean Absolute Error)	2.11
R ² (Coefficient of Determination)	0.997
Log Marginal Likelihood	209.44
Noise Variance σ^2	0.01
Coverage $\pm 1\sigma$	93.3
Coverage $\pm 2\sigma$	100
Shapiro–Wilk W (normality)	0.93
Shapiro–Wilk p (normality)	3.50E-11

Visual Inspection of country plots: All stable.

2025 Grand Total of $\sum EX$ (difference from paper)	1099 (-1)
2050 “	1491 (0)
2075 “	1662 (-2)
2100 “	1597 (+31)

Feature (most influential six in the paper in green)	LengthScale ℓ_d
tas	1.20
pr	2.03
POP	4.77
GSATA_global	6.41
rx5day	11.52
GDP per capita	23.12
SST_global	100.00
SFCWIND_global	100.00
PR_global	100.00
HDI	100.00
cdd	100.00
cdw	100.00
hd40	100.00
r20mm	100.00
Net migration	100.00

Table Notes: Each change to original specification is in cyan.

4. Initial variable importance analysis

Table 9 Three initial tests used to assess the socioeconomic-climatic predictors

a

Variable	Random Forest ↓	Ridge Regression	Permutation Importance
POP	0.50	0.31	5.14
GDP	0.29	0.00	2.93
tas	0.04	0.06	0.46
rx5day	0.03	0.01	0.12
hd40	0.03	0.03	0.24
HDI	0.02	0.06	0.00
pr	0.02	0.13	-0.05
Net migration	0.01	0.01	0.05
r20mm	0.01	0.10	-0.04
cdd	0.01	0.01	0.00
cdw	0.01	0.11	0.10
PR_global	0.01	0.08	-0.04
GSATA_global	0.00	0.02	-0.03
SFCWIND_global	0.00	0.01	0.01
SST_global	0.00	0.06	0.00

b

Model	Train RMSE	Test RMSE	CV RMSE Mean	CV RMSE std (σ)
Random Forest	2.20	3.49	4.36	± 3.33
Ridge Regression	4.91	5.18	9.45	± 10.02
Permutation Importance	2.20	3.49	4.36	± 3.33

c

Parameter	Value	Purpose / Overfitting Impact
<i>Random Forest</i>		
n_estimators	100	Number of trees in the forest (more = more stable)
max_depth	6	Controls model complexity (prevents overfitting)
random_state	42	Ensures reproducibility
train_test_split	80/20	Used to evaluate generalization
cross_val_score	5-fold CV	Assesses variance and overfitting risk
<i>Ridge Regression</i>		

c

Parameter	Value	Purpose / Overfitting Impact
alpha	1.0	L2 regularization strength (higher = less overfitting)
train_test_split	80/20	Test set used to check generalization
cross_val_score	5-fold CV	Captures model stability
StandardScaler	Applied	Prevents variable scale from inflating coefficients

Permutation Importance

model	Same as in Random Forest	Shares same setup and overfitting controls as Random Forest
n_repeats	10	More repeats = more stable estimates
scoring	neg_root_mean_squared_error	Reflects error sensitivity

Table Notes: a, Importance tests of predicting with $\sum EX$ three different models from [scikit-learn](https://scikit-learn.org/). More red, more important. Both random forest and ridge regression add up to 1.00. Their colour scale is the same whereas permutation importance is separate. b, Diagnostics of models. RMSE = Root Mean Squared Error. CV = Cross Validation. c, Hyperparameters and inputs for the models.

5. Preliminary assessments of the dataset

Correlation

Figure 3 Correlation heatmap of variables

Figure Notes: Some clusters can already be noticed. For example, nominal people at risk ΣEX is most correlated with POP and GDP . The global climate change variables are highly correlated with each other except for surface wind ($SFCWIND_global$). The “extreme weather” indicators are well correlated with each other either positively or negatively – the determining factor seemingly being if it is a “wet” or a “dry” indicator.

Multicollinearity

Table 10 Multicollinearity test with Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Variable	VIF ↓	Variable	VIF (cont. ↓)
GSATΔ_global	305.8	POP	6.6
PR_global	174.4	ΣEX	5.4
SST_global	158.3	GDP	3.3
pr	46.2	hd40	3.2
cdw	27.9	HDI	2.6
r20mm	14.1	tas	2.4
rx5day	8.6	SFCWIND_global	1.5
cdd	7.5	Net migration	1.0

Table Notes: VIF ≈ 1: No multicollinearity (ideal). VIF > 5: Moderate multicollinearity (potential concern). VIF > 10: High multicollinearity (serious issue, might need to remove or reduce variables).

Autocorrelation

Figure 4 Heatmap of Autocorrelation Function (ACF) test

Figure Notes: Positive values (close to 1) have a strong persistence, meaning past values influence future values. Negative values indicate oscillatory behaviour (reversal in trend). Near-zero values suggest that past values have little or no influence on future values. Gradual decay in ACF values across lags: If autocorrelation declines slowly, the variable has a long memory (high persistence). If it drops quickly to near zero, the variable is more random and has less predictive power based on past values.

Heteroskedasticity

Table 11 Breusch-Pagan heteroskedasticity test

Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	p-value	F-statistic	F-statistic p-value
121.19	1.11E-18	12.53	4.59E-24

Table Notes: p-value < 0.05 is and we reject the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity. Thus, heteroskedasticity exists in the original dataset and the spread of data points is inconsistent, and errors get larger as values increase as Figure 5 below shows.

Figure 5 Heteroskedasticity test visualized

Stationarity

Table 12 Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test for stationarity

Variable	ADF I(0) ↓	p-value I(0)	ADF I(1)	p-value I(1)
cdd	-13.89	5.95E-26		
pr	-12.10	2.00E-22		
cdw	-11.80	9.45E-22		
r20mm	-9.40	6.11E-16		
rx5day	-8.19	7.58E-13		
tas	-7.53	3.63E-11		
hd40	-2.82	5.49E-02		
POP	-2.61	9.20E-02	-7.88	4.76E-12
SFCWIND_global	-2.04	2.69E-01	-17.55	4.14E-30
ΣEX	-1.26	6.45E-01	-8.75	2.93E-14
GDP	-0.87	7.97E-01	-6.57	7.96E-09
PR_global	0.72	9.90E-01	-17.70	3.55E-30
GSATA_global	0.76	9.91E-01	-17.71	3.49E-30
SST_global	0.84	9.92E-01	-17.71	3.52E-30
HDI	1.27	9.96E-01	-9.10	3.58E-15

Table Notes: The blue variables were stationary at levels I(0) with a critical ADF value of 5% (-2.86) and p-value < 0.05. After first differencing I(1), all the rest of the variables are stationary with the same thresholds. Net migration was added later to dataset and is not present here. Note that differencing was not done for the dataset used in the paper.

Table 13 Engle-Granger pairwise cointegration test

Variable	ADF ↓	p-value
HDI	-10.70	4.48E-18
GSATA_global	-5.05	1.34E-04
SST_global	-4.99	1.75E-04
POP	-4.74	4.82E-04
GDP	-4.74	4.84E-04
PR_global	-4.68	6.09E-04
SFCWIND_global	-1.96	5.51E-01

Table Notes: This checks if the I(1) variables have a long-term relationship with ΣEX. At a critical ADF value of 5% (-3.36) and p-value < 0.05, the blue variables are cointegrated with ΣEX and move together long-term.

6. Baseline country graphs

Below we show all individual country graphs of the GRP's baseline model's predictions and the observed historic values as well as the projections of INFORM Climate Change for 2050 and 2080. They comprise Σ EX (nominal people at risk), PIN (real people in need), funding requirement, and POP for each country 2000–2100. Better quality and all country graphs are stored openly on <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15336209>.

Figure 6 The 26 baseline country plots from the Gaussian Process Regression.

7. Marginal effect plots of the predictors

In Figure 7, the marginal effect of the highest six climatic-socioeconomic drivers (Table 3) on the number of people at risk in each country is available.

Figure 7 Marginal effect plots of the six most influential predictors per country

Figure Notes: Created with LOESS (Locally Estimated Scatterplot Smoothing). Steep upward red line means strong, positive relationship (e.g., higher temperature results in more exposed people). A downward line shows higher values reduce exposure. Flat line indicates that the predictor is not influential for that country.

8. Extended data

Figure 8 Simulations until 2100

Figure Notes: **a, b** The same plots as in the paper but now extended to 2100. **c** Annual inflation of 1%, 2% and 3% is added to the steady-state baseline starting from 2024 as a comparison. The y-axis is capped at 545, the same as in **b**, for easier comparison even if 3% inflation would go higher.

Figure 9 Summary chart of the simulations

Summary at 25-year intervals of the data (Figure 8) with the same y-axis scale and cumulative (2025-2100) totals of the simulations and reference data. Note that in the cumulative chart, both units jump to a higher order of magnitude of billion and trillion.

Figure 10 Sparklines of the 26 countries' simulations

Sparklines of each country's simulation with the same data and coding as in Figure 8. The y-scale is not shown and is not the same for any of the panels as they are meant to display the general trend of each country. Larger figures of each country's baseline are in the previous section.

9. List of Figures and Tables

Figure 1 Distribution of exposure drivers	9
Figure 2 Global residuals of the GPR model	14
Figure 3 Correlation heatmap of variables	24
Figure 4 Heatmap of Autocorrelation Function (ACF) test	25
Figure 5 Heteroskedasticity test visualized	26
Figure 6 The 26 baseline country plots from the Gaussian Process Regression.	31
Figure 7 Marginal effect plots of the six most influential predictors per country	33
Figure 8 Simulations until 2100.....	34
Figure 9 Summary chart of the simulations.....	35
Figure 2 Sparklines of the 26 countries' simulations	36
Table 1 Descriptions of variables	2
Table 2 Descriptive statistics of the dataset.....	4
Table 3 Climate risk indicators per length scale	6
Table 4 The 26 analysed countries with their 2022 ND-GAIN score	7
Table 5 Global diagnostics of the final Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) model	12
Table 6 Country-level diagnostics	13
Table 7 Cross-Validation (CV) and nested CV diagnostics.....	13
Table 8 Robustness tests by modifying hyperparameters (a-e) and GDP (f)	16
Table 9 Three initial tests used to assess the socioeconomic-climatic predictors.....	22
Table 10 Multicollinearity test with Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)	25
Table 11 Breusch-Pagan heteroskedasticity test.....	26
Table 12 Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test for stationarity	27
Table 13 Engle-Granger pairwise cointegration test.....	27